

THERMAL EVALUATION AND PREPARATION OF MORTAR CONTAINING N-HEXADECANE/XGNP SSPCM FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS

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ABSTRACT

Shape-stabilized phase change material (SSPCM) was prepared by impregnating hexadecane, as a PCM, into xGnP, as a supporting material. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy confirmed that the heat storage characteristics of hexadecane could be integrated into the structure of xGnP for its physical bonding, without a change in its chemical properties. Differential scanning calorimeter analysis showed that the melting temperature range of the SSPCM was similar to that of pure hexadecane. Thermo gravimetric analysis of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM determined that the percentage of impregnated hexadecane into xGnP was 48.8 % with 96.4 J/g of latent heat storage energy. In addition, mortar with the prepared SSPCM was investigated in terms of developing advanced building materials with thermal energy storage properties. The heating and cooling behavior test of the SSPCM mortar demonstrated the improvement of the thermal mass and inertia by the mortars containing the SSPCM. Consequently, the thermal behavior of the test buildings made of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar was computationally investigated using Energy Plus. The obtained measurements validated a reduction in temperature variations and an enhancement of thermal inertia, during the time periods examined. Consequently, the thermal behaviors of the test buildings made of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar were computationally investigated using Energy Plus. The measurements obtained demonstrated a reduction in temperature variations and an enhancement of thermal inertia, during the monitored time periods, when the wall is treated with the SSPCM mortar. Hence, an improvement in indoor comfort and a reduction in building energy consumption can be anticipated. The utilization of the new composite SSPCM considerably contribute to the thermal energy storage rate in buildings.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermal energy storage technologies have been developed to promote efficient energy usage with sensible and latent storage types. Especially, the thermal energy storage system using phase change materials (PCM) has been extensively employed in heat applications such as heat power plants and buildings due to its large thermal storage ability in relatively small volumes [1,2]. PCMs have a high latent heat of fusion during phase change. PCMs can charge the heat with melting or discharging it with solidification when they undergo a hot or cold environment [3].

Despite their potential characteristics, they could incur several problems: leakage during the solid-liquid phase change, lower thermal conductivity of PCMs, and limited cycles of melting and solidification. Some researchers have studied ways to resolve the leakage problem of liquid PCMs. Although methods to solve the leakage problem of PCM have been suggested by many researchers, they still showed a low thermal conductivity that has a strong effect on the heat storage efficiency of the materials. All non-metallic liquids, including PCM, have low thermal conductivity. These weaknesses reduce the rate of heat storage and release during the melting and solidification cycles, and limit their broad applications. When fast heat transfer is necessary, one possibility to increase the thermal conductivity of the PCM is to add materials that have larger thermal conductivity. Many ways to enhance the thermal conductivity of PCM have been attempted.

This research prepared SSPCM to solve the leakage problem, developing their efficient thermal storage quantity, improving the thermal conductivity, and retaining the mechanical stability by forming a composite material using a porous material with a PCM. Hexadecane was used as a heat storage material, as it has a suitable temperature range of a comfortable indoor environment. Exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets (xGnP), which is a porous nano-sized carbon material, was used to improve the thermal conductivity and heat storage efficiency as a supporting structure to make the PCM incorporated into it on a microscopic scale.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Hexadecane, $C_{16}H_{34}$, is made of the alkane series and belongs to the organic PCMs. It has good storage density with respect to mass, as well as melts and solidifies correspondingly with little or no subcooling. Hexadecane is not soluble in water as water repellents and compatible with metals.

xGnP is a graphitic carbon-based material. The graphite was sourced from Asbury Graphite Mills, Inc., NJ, USA, by applying a cost- and time-effective exfoliation process initially proposed by the Drzal group [4]. xGnP incorporates the layered structure and low price of nanoclays with the superior mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of carbon nanotubes. In addition, it is very cost effective and can provide a multitude of physical and chemical property improvements [5-8]. Table 1 shows the physical properties of hexadecane and xGnP.

2.2 Preparation of hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM

Hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM was prepared by the impregnation method in a vacuum. Figure 1 shows the vacuum impregnation equipment. xGnP dried at 105 °C for 24 hours, was preliminarily located in a filtering flask that was connected to a water trap apparatus to evacuate air from the porous surface of the xGnP. Then, the valve between the flask and a container with hexadecane in liquid state was unlocked to flow it into the flask to dampen the xGnP sample. The vacuum process was continued for 60 min, and then air was permitted to enter the flask again to force the liquid PCM to permeate into the pore space of the xGnP. The hexadecane/xGnP composite in colloidal state was filtered by an 1 μ m glass fiber filter paper and was dried in a vacuum drier at 80 °C for 24 hours. Figure 2 is an image of the appearance of xGnP and hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM at 10 °C. xGnP is a type of black powder, and the prepared hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM is a type of black granule.

Physical properties	Hexadecane	xGnP
Melting temperature (°C)	18.0	-
Heat storage capacity (J/g)	257.7	-
Specific heat capacity (J/g·K)	65.1	-
Density liquid at 40 °C (kg/l)	0.77	-
Thermal conductivity (W/m·K)	0.39	2-300
Specific heat capacity (J/kg·K)	-	710
Surface area (m ² /g)	-	20.41
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	-	0.0053-0.010
Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	-	0.081

Table 1: Physical properties of hexadecane and xGnP

Figure 1: Vacuum equipment to prepare SSPCM.

Figure 2: (a) xGnP and (b) hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM (at 10°C).

2.3 Characterization techniques of hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM

The microstructure of samples was represented by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at room temperature. A SEM with an accelerating voltage of 12 kV and a working distance of 12 mm was used to collect the SEM images.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR: 300E Jasco) was also employed to monitor the change of chemical groups. The samples were analyzed over the range of 500 – 4000 cm^{-1} with a spectrum resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . All spectra were averaged over 32 scans. This analysis of xGnP, hexadecane, and the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM was performed at a point-to-point contact with a pressure device [9].

Thermal conductivities of pure hexadecane and the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM were measured by TCi thermal conductivity analyzer, with a 20 mm diameter and 10 mm thickness, in a cool cube box at 10 °C to prevent its phase changing from solid state to liquid at lab temperature. The TCi can measure thermal conductivity of small specimens using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) method [10, 11].

Thermal properties, such as melting temperature and latent heat capacity of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM, were determined using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC Q1000). DSC measurements were executed at a 5 °C/min heating and cooling rate and temperature ranges of 0 to 80 °C and 80 to 0 °C, respectively. Thermo gravimetric analysis measurements of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM were performed using thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA Q5000) on approximately 2 – 4 mg samples, over the temperature range 25 – 600 °C, at a heating rate of 10 °C/min, under a nitrogen flow of 20 ml/min [12].

2.4 Preparation of hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar

The material was mixed with mortar for different contents of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM, 10, 20, and 30 %, as percentages of the cement mass content. The water : cement ratio was 1 : 2, and the sand : cement ratio was 1 : 2. After casting and surface finishing samples were finished, the hexadecane/xGnP mortar was stored in water containers at 20 °C for 28 curing days.

Figure 3: Heating and cooling behavior test setup; (a) turned off and (b) turned on.

Figure 4: SEM images of (a) xGnP and (b) hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM.

2.5 Thermal characterization techniques of hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar

All samples for the thermal conductivity measurement were prepared by TCi thermal conductivity analyzer, with the size of 100 mm × 100 mm × 20 mm (l × w × t). The method is not applicable when a phase change occurs in the material, as might be the case with the PCM containing mixes. The samples were heated to 30 °C, which is the temperature at which pure hexadecane is completely in the liquid state, to overcome the problem.

A heating and cooling behavior experimental setup were constructed, as presented in Figure 3, to measure the influence of the SSPCM contents on the heat storage ability. The sample shape for this test measured 300 mm × 300 mm × 20 mm (l × w × t). The heating and cooling time were each of 8 hours, so total duration time of this test was 16 hours. Thermocouples (type T) were positioned on the front and back sides of samples to measure the temperature during the heating and cooling time. The data was recorded using a data logger, LOGGER GL800 by Graphtec.

2.6 Design of computational analysis of hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar

This study was performed on test buildings located in Seoul, the Republic of Korea. The test buildings have a floor above ground level and 5000 mm of a cubicle shape. The properties of materials used in the test buildings construction were obtained from 2009 ASHRAE Standard [13], as presented in Table 2. The window frames are made of wood and have a single glass with 0.900 W/m·K of thermal conductivity. Specific heat and enthalpy of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar changes dynamically at each time step of the calculation as a function of the local temperature. Practically, the solid-liquid phase change of PCM is taken into account by implementing the effective heat capacity method [14]. This computational analysis was performed aimed at comparing the thermal behaviors of walls characterized by the mortar boards that have different contents of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM located in the most inner side of the wall. Four types of test buildings were monitored during the year.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Properties of hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM

Scanning electron microscopy observations were performed for the xGnP and hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM in Figure 4. In Figure 4-(b), hexadecane is seen to be uniformly incorporated into the pores of the xGnP.

	Material	Thermal conductivity (W/m·K)	Thermal capacity (J/kg·K)	Density (kg/m ³)	Thickness (mm)
Wall	Metallic caldding	0.290	1000	1250	6
	XPS	0.034	1400	35	90
	SSPCM mortar	Variable	Variable	1600	20
Ceiling	Asphalt	0.700	1000	2100	10
	Glass wool	0.040	840	12	150
	Air gap	0.180	-	-	200
	Plasterboard	0.250	896	2800	15
Floor	Urea formaldehyde foam	0.040	1400	10	130
	Cast concrete	1.130	1000	2000	100
	Floor/roof screed	0.410	840	1200	70
	Timber flooring	0.140	1200	650	30

Table 2: Thermal and physical properties of test buildings

Figure 5: (a) Heating & cooling behavior and (b) Thermal conductivity of mortar

FTIR absorption spectra of the xGnP, the hexadecane and the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM explain there is no chemical interaction between the hexadecane and the xGnP. Subsequently, it was demonstrated that the heat storage characteristics of hexadecane could be integrated into the structure of xGnP due to its physical bonding without a change in its chemical properties.

The influence of xGnP on hexadecane to enhance the thermal transition ability was confirmed by thermal conductivity test using TCi. The thermal conductivity of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM increased 3.5 times at 10 °C, compared to the pure hexadecane. It is obviously indicated that the impregnating of hexadecane into xGnP results in increased thermal transition ability for thermal storage during heat absorption and release.

DSC analysis was performed for the thermal properties of the samples. The specific heat of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM abruptly increased during the transition temperature range of the SSPCM from solid to liquid state, and reaches a peak point in the liquid state as a whole. The specific heat of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM is 10.0 J/g·K at 21.8 °C. The heating and freezing curves from the DSC of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM are presented in Figure 5-(a). This high latent heat storage of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM has an important potential in heating and cooling applications as building materials.

TGA tests were performed to determine the percentage of impregnation of the SSPCM ranging from 20 °C to 600 °C. Decomposition of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM sharply started from 100.0 °C and ended at 205.0 °C. As xGnP is a carbon-based material that has thermal resistance properties, it could not decompose in the tested temperature range. In other words, all of the decomposed material was hexadecane, and the percentage of impregnated hexadecane was 48.8 %.

Figure 6: (a) Heating and cooling behaviors of mortar and (b) Overheating and overcooling degree hours of test buildings for a year.

3.2 Thermal behavior of hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar

Thermal conductivity measurements were obtained such as Figure 5-(b). This shows that the addition of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM into the mass of the mortar lead to a small increase in thermal conductivity. Therefore, there was an improvement in the thermal transfer of building materials for effective heat storage performance during heating and cooling by impregnating the hexadecane into the xGnP.

In the this work, the above designated heating and cooling behavior analysis device such as Figure 3 was used to simulate indoor and outdoor temperatures. Evaluation of the thermal performance of building materials used for building envelopes was executed by measuring the decrease in temperature and time lag. During the heating process, the outdoor temperature was assumed to have a range from 28 °C to 30 °C for 8 hours. The measured temperature on the inner side of the sample was acquaint with a measure of the total heat lag among the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortars for the indoor environment. When the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM-free mortar and the 30 % SSPCM contents were compared, the temperature measurements during the heating time revealed an up to 4.9 °C of maximum variation at an early 306 min (at $x = 306$ min), and 157 min of time lag effect, until the inner side of the sample reached 17.5 °C (at $y = 17.5$ °C). Moreover, the temperature measurements during cooling time determined an up to 4.1 °C of maximum temperature variation after the start of cooling at 275 min (at $x = 755$ min), and 132 min of time lag effect, until the inner side of the sample peaked at 15.9 °C (at $y = 15.9$ °C) such as Figure 6-(a).

3.3 Computational analysis of hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar integrated in test buildings

The internal air temperature variation for five days in the test buildings in winter and summer time were simulated as presented in Figure 7. In winter, the maximum calculated temperature in the PCM treated test house was approximately 9.1 °C higher than the respective maximum value of the non-treated test house (the control). The minimum temperature in the test house retaining the SSPCM mortar 30 % was 11.7 °C higher than in the non-treated test house. The cooling process was predicted to be smoother for the test house containing the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar, indicating that the stored energy is gradually released. During summer, temperatures rarely attain values below 18.0 °C. Therefore, PCM with a characteristic phase change range around 18.0 °C remains in the liquid phase and cannot be discharged by releasing the absorbed heat. The above results and approach can be used to optimize material properties corresponding to indoor comfort conditions. Thus, it is indicated that the developed computational approach, in conjunction with basic experiments can be used to determine the optimum percentage and type of PCM to be implemented in the material to achieve predefined energy profiles.

Figure 6-(b) shows that as the content of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM in the mortar increased, the overheating and overcooling degree hours of the test buildings for a year were reduced 13.0 kKhr/a in the test building constructed with the 30 % SSPCM mortar, about 15.7 % improvement in energy efficiency.

Figure 7: Internal air temperature of test buildings integrated with SSPCM mortar (a) in winter and (b) in summer.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This research developed a product that could realize important building energy savings, with the improvement of heat storage mortar, using an innovative type of phase change material, with respect to its thermal properties. The work presented the preparation of new thermally developed SSPCM, and introduced thermal storage mortar as a building material. The hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM was developed to prevent from leakage, while retaining efficient thermal storage capacity. Hexadecane with a melting temperature 18.0 °C was used as the PCM. xGnP that is a porous nano-sized carbon material was a good container for the PCM, due to its highly porous nature, high surface area, and high thermal conductivity. According to the TGA data, hexadecane was impregnated into xGnP by as much as 48.8 % of the prepared SSPCM composite. The hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM had a melting temperature range of 16.0 °C to 25.0 °C, with 96.4 J/g of thermal storage capacity, and a freezing temperature range 17.0 °C to 12.0 °C, with 94.8 J/g of thermal release capacity. The thermal properties of mortar mixed with the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM were identified. It was useful in real applications, as a finishing material in buildings. The property tests demonstrated the tested mortar showed a good time-lag effect during heating, and reservation of temperature during cooling. Consequently, the thermal behaviors of the test buildings made of the hexadecane/xGnP SSPCM mortar were computationally investigated using Energy Plus. The measurements obtained demonstrated a reduction in temperature variations and an enhancement of thermal inertia, during the monitored time periods, when the wall is treated with the SSPCM mortar. Hence, an improvement in indoor comfort and a reduction in building energy consumption can be anticipated. The utilization of the new composite SSPCM considerably contribute to the thermal energy storage rate in buildings.

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